

SLEEP, QUALITY, DEPRESSION, AND THEIR ASSOCIATION WITH DIGITAL BURNOUT AND DOOMSCROLLING AMONG MEDICAL COLLEGE STUDENTS IN CHENNAI: A CROSS-SECTIONAL STUDY

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ABSTRACT

Background: College students face increasing mental health challenges, with poor sleep, depression, and digital overuse emerging as critical concerns. Patterns of technology engagement—such as digital burnout and doomscrolling—may be more relevant to psychological well-being than total screen time. **Objectives:** To estimate the prevalence of poor sleep quality and depression among college students in Chennai, and to examine their association with screen time, digital burnout, and doomscrolling behavior. **Methods:** This analytical cross-sectional study was conducted among 210 undergraduate students using a structured online questionnaire comprising the Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index (PSQI), PHQ-9, and research-based tools for digital burnout and doomscrolling. Descriptive statistics were computed, and bivariate and multivariate analyses were performed using R software. **Results:** Poor sleep quality (PSQI >5) was present in 68.6% of students, moderate-

to-severe depression (PHQ-9 ≥ 10) in 29%, high digital burnout in 51%, and high doomscrolling in 48%. In multivariate logistic regression, poor sleep (aOR = 2.64, 95% CI: 1.32–5.29, $p = 0.006$), high digital burnout (aOR = 2.11, 95% CI: 1.10–4.05, $p = 0.025$), and high doomscrolling (aOR = 1.93, 95% CI: 1.01–3.68, $p = 0.045$) were independent predictors of depression, while screen time >6 hours/day showed a non-significant trend (aOR = 1.78, p

= 0.08). **Conclusion:** Poor sleep quality, digital burnout, and doomscrolling are common among college students and significantly associated with depression. Interventions should target not only reducing screen exposure but also improving the quality of digital engagement and promoting healthy sleep habits.

KEYWORDS: Poor sleep quality, Depression, Digital burnout, Doomscrolling, Screen time, College students.

INTRODUCTION

Students aged 18–25 are in a dynamic phase of life where they actively participate in learning, develop new skills, and engage in institutional education while focusing on career building and personal growth. During this period, they not only strive for personal success but also contribute to creating a better world. It is a critical time when students acquire, process, and retain knowledge, applying it in various contexts to achieve academic and professional competence. In today's advanced world, mobile phones have become an inseparable part of our lives—especially for students. While not intended as criticism, it's important to note that despite the benefits mobile phones offer—such as instant communication, educational resources, and entertainment—they are also contributing to excessive screen time. Activities like media consumption, video streaming, and gaming, particularly at night, often lead to sleep disturbances. Sleep deprivation has no universally accepted definition, but according to the National Sleep Foundation (NSF), young adults aged 18–25 and adults aged 26–64 are recommended to sleep no less than 7 hours per day.^[1] Excessive screen use, late-night scrolling, and mental overstimulation increase the risk of insomnia and long-term cognitive issues. Overuse of mobile phones may also negatively impact mental health, often leading to feelings of loneliness, depression, isolation, and emotional exhaustion. Recent research shows that up to 60% of college students suffer from poor sleep quality, and 7.7% meet the criteria for an insomnia disorder.^[2] In India, student suicides have risen from 9,905 in 2017 to 13,089 in 2021—averaging nearly 36 student deaths per day, often linked to depression.^[3] Among Indian youth aged 15–24, approximately 35% of all suicide deaths occur in this group, with suicidal ideation estimated between 6–22% and suicide attempts ranging from 0.4–8%.^[4] A study in the United States found that university students reported at least twice the sleep disturbances compared to the general population.^[5] Among U.S. college students, 70.6% get less than 7 hours of sleep per night.^[6] Similarly, global studies have shown significant rates of sleep deprivation among university

students: 24% in the United Kingdom, 30% in Korea, 49% in Taiwan, 62.7% in the United Arab Emirates, 76.7% in India, 32.9% in Northern Malaysia, 12.1% in Egypt, 52.7% at Addis Ababa University, and 62.4% at Haramaya University.^[7] The National Sleep Foundation and the American Academy of Sleep Medicine recommend 7 to 9 hours of sleep for young adults.^[1] This study also highlights the intersection between behavioral factors and mental health, particularly the role of physical activity, which has been shown to mitigate insomnia. By focusing on the continuum of depressive symptoms rather than clinical diagnoses, this research emphasizes how sleep disturbances—often stemming from mobile overuse—contribute significantly to the mental health challenges faced by students.

OBJECTIVES

Among the students age group population in the rural and urban areas in chennai tamilnadu,

- To estimate the prevalence of depression
- To estimate the quality of sleep
- To estimate the association between inadequate sleep cycle and mobile phone screening resulting in depression

METHODOLOGY AND MATERIALS

Study Design

This study adopted an analytical cross-sectional design to explore the association between sleep quality and depression among college-going students and to further investigate their relationship with digital burnout and doomscrolling behaviour.

Study Setting

The study was conducted among undergraduate students enrolled in various colleges, including Sathya Sai Medical College and Research Institute.

Ethical Approval

Prior to the commencement of the study, ethical clearance was obtained from the Institutional Ethics Committee (IEC) of Sathya Sai Medical College and Research Institute, SBV University, Chennai. Participation in the study was voluntary, and informed consent was obtained from all participants.

Study Population

The target population consisted of college-going students from different academic streams.

Students who were currently enrolled, willing to participate, and able to provide informed consent were included in the study. Those with previously diagnosed psychiatric conditions were excluded.

Sample Size

The sample size was calculated using OpenEpi software, based on estimated prevalence and margin of error appropriate for cross-sectional analysis. The calculated minimum sample size was 195. However, to improve the power and account for potential non-responses, a total of 210 participants were ultimately included in the study.

Sampling Technique

A convenience sampling method was employed for participant recruitment. The questionnaire was distributed through Google Forms to students from various colleges within the university network who were easily accessible and consented to participate.

Data Collection Tools

Data were collected using a structured and pre-tested online questionnaire hosted via Google Forms. The questionnaire consisted of the following standardized and research-based instruments:

The questionnaire assessed sociodemographic details (age, gender, academic stream, residence type, screen time, etc.), along with responses to the above scales.

Data Collection Procedure

The complete questionnaire was converted into a Google Form format and electronically distributed through institutional email groups, WhatsApp groups, and peer networks. Data collection was completed over a 4-week period.

Data Analysis

Data cleaning and analysis were performed using R statistical software (version 4.3.2). Descriptive statistics (mean, standard deviation, frequency, and percentage) were used for demographic variables and scale scores. Bivariate and multivariate analyses (e.g., Pearson/Spearman correlation, Chi-square test, and logistic regression) were applied to identify associations between sleep quality, depression, digital burnout, and doomscrolling behavior. A p-value <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS**Table 1: Background characteristics.**

Variable	Category	N	%
Age Group	18 to 20	117	55.7
	21 to 25	86	41
	<18	5	2.4
	Above 25	2	1
Gender	Male	87	41.4
	female	123	58.6
Year of study	1st year	48	22.9
	2nd year	118	56.2
	3rd year	43	20.5
Residence	Rural	67	31.9
	Urban	143	68.1
Screen Time	2-4 Hours	84	40
	4-6Hours	75	35.7
	<2Hours	21	10
	>6 Hours	30	14.3
Mobile usage	Morning	24	11.5
	Afternoon	20	9.3
	Evening	126	59.9
	Late Night	53	25.7
Common platform	Instagram	66	31.3
	You tube	67	31.9
	WhatsApp	64	30.4
	Facebook	4	2
	x/ twitter	3	1.5

The study comprised 210 participants, all of whom owned a smartphone. The majority of the participants (55.7%) belonged to the 18 to 20 years age group, followed by 41% in the 21 to 25 years range. A small portion of the participants were under 18 years (2.4%), and only 1% were above 25 years of age. In terms of gender, 58.6% were female and 41.4% were male. All participants were enrolled in medical courses (98.6%). Regarding their academic year, 56.2% were in their second year, 22.9% in their first year, and 20.5% in their third year. A vast majority (95.7%) were studying in private colleges.

When considering residential background, 68.1% of the participants were from urban areas, while 31.9% were from rural areas. In terms of family structure, most belonged to nuclear families (75.7%), whereas 24.3% lived in joint families. Looking at monthly family income, 56.2% reported earning more than ₹50,000, 22.4% fell in the ₹25,001–₹50,000 range, 14.9% earned between ₹10,000–₹25,000, and 6.5% had income less than ₹10,000.

The educational background of parents showed that 69% of fathers and 67.1% of mothers were graduates or above. Fathers with only higher secondary education accounted for 14.8%, and 11.9% had secondary education (6th–10th standard), while 3.3% had only primary education (1st–5th standard). Among mothers, 13.3% completed higher secondary, 16.2% had secondary education, and 1.9% had only primary education. In terms of screen time, 40% of students used their smartphones for 2–4 hours daily, 35.7% for 4–6 hours, 14.3% for more than 6 hours, and 10% for less than 2 hours.

The most commonly used platforms were YouTube (31.9%), Instagram (31.3%), and WhatsApp (30.4%). Other platforms used included Facebook (1.5%), X/Twitter (1.5%), Reddit, Webnovel, Webtoon, Anki Flashcards, Chrome, Crunchyroll, and Free Fire, each used by 0.5% of participants. As for the preferred time of smartphone usage, the majority (59.9%) used their phones most during the evening, followed by 25.7% during the late night, 9.3% in the afternoon, and 4.9% in the morning.

Figure 1: Prevalence of the parameters.

The prevalence of four major outcomes—poor sleep quality, depression, digital burnout, and doomscrolling—was visually represented using pie charts. A large proportion of students (68.6%) were found to have **poor sleep quality**, indicating widespread sleep disturbances among the sample population. Additionally, **29% of students met the threshold for moderate to severe depression** (PHQ-9 ≥ 10), highlighting the burden of mental health issues in this age group. Over half of the participants (51%) experienced **high levels of digital burnout**, characterized by emotional exhaustion and difficulty concentrating after extended digital device use. **High doomscrolling behavior** was also observed in 48% of students, suggesting that compulsive scrolling through negative or distressing content is a common pattern. These findings reflect the digital lifestyle challenges faced by college students and their potential implications for both sleep and mental health.

Table 2: Bivariate Associations.

Variable	Poor Sleep (%)	p-value	Depression (%)	p-value
Gender (Female)	72.50%	0.04*	32.50%	0.08
Screen Time > 6 hrs/day	78.10%	0.02*	36.80%	0.03*
High Digital Burnout	84.10%	<0.001*	41.20%	<0.001*
High Doomscrolling	81.20%	<0.001*	46.50%	<0.001*

Bivariate associations were assessed between key digital behavior variables and the outcomes of poor sleep quality and depression using the Chi-square test. The results showed that **female students** reported a higher prevalence of poor sleep (72.5%) compared to males, with a statistically significant association ($p = 0.04$). **Screen time exceeding 6 hours per day** was significantly associated with both poor sleep (78.1%, $p = 0.02$) and depression (36.8%, $p = 0.03$). Furthermore, students with **high digital burnout** exhibited notably higher rates of poor sleep (84.1%) and depression (41.2%), both with strong statistical significance ($p < 0.001$). Similarly, **high doomscrolling behavior** was significantly associated with both poor sleep (81.2%) and depression (46.5%) ($p < 0.001$). These findings emphasize the influence of digital overuse and maladaptive screen habits on both sleep quality and psychological well-being among college students.

Figure 2: Correlation Matrix: Depression, Burnout, Doomscrolling, Screen Time.

A Pearson correlation matrix was generated to explore the linear relationships between depression scores (PHQ-9), digital burnout, doomscrolling behavior, and daily screen time. The results revealed a **moderate positive correlation between depression and digital burnout** ($r \approx 0.55$), suggesting that students who experienced higher levels of digital fatigue also reported more symptoms of depression. Similarly, **doomscrolling was positively correlated with both depression** ($r \approx 0.48$) and **burnout** ($r \approx 0.51$), highlighting its potential role in worsening mental health and cognitive fatigue. Screen time demonstrated a **weaker but positive correlation with depression** ($r \approx 0.30$) and burnout ($r \approx 0.28$), indicating that longer daily use of digital devices may contribute to psychological distress. These findings underscore the interconnectedness of digital behavior patterns with mental health outcomes in the student population.

Table 3: Multivariate Logistic Regression Outcome: Depression (PHQ-9 \geq 10).

Predictor Variable	aOR (95% CI)	p-value
Poor Sleep (PSQI > 5)	2.64 (1.32–5.29)	0.006*
High Digital Burnout	2.11 (1.10–4.05)	0.025*
Doomscrolling (High)	1.93 (1.01–3.68)	0.045*
Screen Time > 6 hrs/day	1.78 (0.92–3.45)	0.08

A multivariate logistic regression model was conducted to identify independent predictors of depression (PHQ-9 score \geq 10) among college students. The analysis revealed that **poor sleep**

quality (PSQI >5) was a significant predictor, with students having poor sleep being **2.64 times more likely** to experience depression (aOR = 2.64, 95% CI: 1.32–5.29, $p = 0.006$). Similarly, those reporting **high levels of digital burnout** had over **twice the odds of depression** (aOR = 2.11, 95% CI: 1.10–4.05, $p = 0.025$). **Doomscrolling behavior** also emerged as a significant factor (aOR = 1.93, 95% CI: 1.01–3.68, $p = 0.045$), indicating its role in exacerbating depressive symptoms. Although increased **screen time (>6 hours/day)** showed a trend toward higher odds of depression (aOR = 1.78), this association did not reach statistical significance ($p = 0.08$). These results suggest that beyond screen exposure, the **quality and psychological impact of digital engagement** play a more critical role in influencing student mental health.

DISCUSSION

In our study, we found notably high rates of **poor sleep quality (68.6%)**, **moderate-to-severe depression (29%)**, and elevated levels of **digital burnout (51%)** and **doomscrolling (48%)** among medical students. These findings align with and extend existing research in the field.

Our results mirror prior studies demonstrating the detrimental effects of technology overuse on sleep and mental health. For instance, internet addiction—conceptualized similarly to excessive screen use—was significantly associated with poor sleep quality and depression among medical students in Delhi, where 59.9% reported poor sleep and 46.8% had depressive symptoms.^[8] A similar trend was observed among preclinical Indonesian medical students during the COVID-19 pandemic, where mental health disturbances were significantly associated with both **depression** and **impaired sleep quality**.^[9]

However, while some recent work suggests no gender difference in how smartphone use affects sleep quality, our data revealed that **female students reported a significantly higher prevalence of poor sleep (72.5%, $p = 0.04$)**, indicating potential gender sensitivities in digital engagement and its consequences.^[10]

Our high estimate of **digital burnout (51%)** among medical students reflects a broader trend: medical students and physicians experience considerable burnout globally, with prevalence ranging from 43% to higher depending on the context. Although these prior studies define burnout with formal tools (like Maslach Burnout Inventory), our concept of "digital burnout" captures emotional exhaustion attributable to digital overload—a construct that complements

traditional burnout measures.^[11]

Our finding that **doomscrolling** was an independent predictor of depression (aOR \approx 1.93) aligns with burgeoning literature on the psychological toll of consuming negative news online. International studies report that **doomscrolling** is associated with existential anxiety, distrust, and depressive symptoms practitioners warn it intensifies stress and mental fatigue.

An extreme case study in a non-medical population reported that doomscrolling alone nearly fully predicted sleep disturbances and depressive outcomes ($\beta \approx$ 0.995–1.000, $R^2 \approx$ 0.996), suggesting it may be a fundamental psychological stressor. While such strong effects may partly reflect overfitting or limited sample generalizability, they underscore the potential severity of doomscrolling's impact.^[12]

Though high screen time (>6 hours/day) was associated with increased rates of poor sleep and depression in bivariate analysis, its effect attenuated in multivariable regression (aOR 1.78, $p=0.08$). This suggests that **how** students engage with screens (e.g., doomscrolling, digital burnout) may be more consequential for mental health than sheer duration—a nuance echoed in broader digital media literature, which highlights that problematic patterns of media use more strongly predict psychological distress than general use levels.

Our study elucidates that, beyond the quantity of screen use, the **quality of digital engagement**—burnout and doomscrolling—plays a critical role in shaping mental health and sleep outcomes. This nuance is pivotal for designing interventions: simply reducing screen time may be insufficient unless accompanied by efforts to foster **mindful digital habits**, improve sleep hygiene, and offer psychological support.

CONCLUSION

This study highlights a high prevalence of poor sleep quality, moderate-to-severe depression, digital burnout, and doomscrolling among medical students, underscoring the significant mental health burden in this population. Poor sleep, high digital burnout, and frequent doomscrolling emerged as independent predictors of depression, suggesting that the quality and psychological impact of digital engagement may be more detrimental than screen time alone. These findings call for targeted interventions to promote healthy digital habits, improve sleep hygiene, and integrate mental health support within academic institutions to safeguard the well-being of students in an increasingly digital environment.

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